

N, N-Diphenylthiourea—An Effective Reagent for the Separation and Determination of all the Platinum Metals.

S. C. SHOME, M. MAZUMDAR and M. K. CHAKRABARTI

Presidency College, Calcutta.

N, N-Diphenylthiourea has been recommended as a sensitive and selective analytical reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of all the platinum metals. The platinum metals form stable complexes with the chelating agent under different experimental conditions. By the use of this organic reagent each of the platinum metals can be determined spectrophotometrically in presence of commonly associated base metals and other platinum metals. A simple method for the separation and determination of the individual platinum metals from their synthetic mixtures has been described.

SEVERAL organic chelating agents¹⁻⁶ have been proposed for the spectrophotometric determination of the platinum metals, but none of them can be recommended for the separation and individual determination of all those metals. A survey of literature indicates that various attempts have been made to improve upon the selectivity and sensitivity of the colour reactions of thiourea with the platinum metals by the introduction of different types of groups at both the nitrogen atoms,^{7,8} and the success so far achieved was only to a limited extent. In the present paper unsymmetrical diphenylthiourea [(C₆H₅)₂.N.CS. NH₂] has been employed as a new sensitive and selective reagent for the microdetermination of each of the platinum metals in presence of commonly associated base metals and other platinum metals.

N, N-Diphenylthiourea (DPT) forms yellow complexes with palladium(II), platinum(IV), ruthenium(III), a pink complex with osmium(VI) and a blue complex with ruthenium(III) in dilute hydrochloric acid medium. The palladium and osmium complexes are formed at room temperature whereas the other metals react with DPT in hot solutions. The chelating agent also forms yellow complexes with platinum(IV), ruthenium(III), iridium(III) and a yellowish brown complex with ruthenium(III) in hot acetate buffer medium. All the metal complexes are extractable in chloroform (except the brown ruthenium complex). Addition of a few ml of ethanol is necessary to remove any scum formed at the interface during extraction. The yellowish brown ruthenium complex can be extracted with methylisobutylketone. DPT has been successfully employed for the separation and determination of the platinum metals by taking advantage of its selectivity in the formation of complexes with those metals under varying experimental conditions such as acidity and temperature of solutions.

Experimental

Apparatus : A Carl-Zeiss spectrophotometer, Model PMQ II, with 1.0 cm quartz cells was used for the absorbance measurements.

A Cambridge (Bench Model) pH meter equipped with glass and calomel electrodes was employed for pH measurements.

Standard platinum metal solutions : The palladium(II), platinum(IV), rhodium(III), iridium(III) and ruthenium(III) solutions were prepared separately by dissolving the corresponding chloride in dilute hydrochloric acid. The osmium(VIII) solution was made by dissolving osmic acid in dilute (0.1N) sodium hydroxide solution. Palladium and platinum contents of the solutions were determined gravimetrically by precipitating each of the metals with thioisocyanamide^{2,8}. Rhodium, iridium and ruthenium contents of the solutions were estimated by the usual hydrolytic precipitation method. Osmium was determined in the solution by precipitation of the metal as sulphide and subsequent ignition in a current of hydrogen. Weaker solutions of the metals for spectrophotometric determination were prepared by dilution of the stock solutions. The platinum metal salts employed were supplied by J. Mathey (U.K).

Diverse ion solutions : Standard solutions of diverse ions were prepared by dissolving weighed amounts of sulphates chlorides, acetates or nitrates of the corresponding metals.

All the reagents used were of analytical grade.

Preparation and properties of the reagent : N, N-diphenylthiourea (DPT) was prepared by hydrolysing N, N-diphenyl-N'-acetyl thiourea with caustic soda solution by the following procedure ; To a 0.1M solution of ammonium thiocyanate in acetone, a 0.1M acetylchloride solution in acetone was added. The mixture was refluxed for 10-15 minutes on a hot water bath, cooled and filtered. To the filtrate, a 0.1M diphenylamine solution in acetone was added and the mixture was refluxed for 10-15 minutes. Excess acetone was removed by distillation. The mixture was then cooled in an ice-bath when yellow crystals of N, N-diphenyl-N'-acetylthiourea separated out. The product after recrystallisation from ethanol was dried and

hydrolysed with a boiling 10% caustic soda solution. It was cooled and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid when N, N-diphenylthiourea (DPT) separated out as white crystals. It was further purified by recrystallisation from ethanol.

DPT is sparingly soluble in water but soluble in ethanol, chloroform and other common organic solvents. The pure compound melts at 212°C. It is stable in strong acid medium. The reagent forms coloured precipitates with all the platinum metals which are sparingly soluble in water but soluble in common organic solvents.

N, N-Diphenylthiourea (DPT) solution: A 0.01M reagent solution in ethanol was used for the spectrophotometric determination of the metal ions.

Adjustment of acidity: The acidities of the solutions were adjusted with dilute hydrochloric acid. Requisite amounts of a 10% solution of sodium acetate were added, where necessary.

Procedure for the spectrophotometric determination of platinum metals

Palladium: A measured amount of the palladium(II) solution was introduced into a 100-ml separatory funnel, diluted with water and its acidity was maintained at 2N-6N. To this, 1-2 ml of 0.01M DPT solution were added, stirred and allowed to stand for 5 minutes, mixed with 2-3 ml of ethanol and the yellow palladium-DPT complex formed was extracted three to four times with 5-ml portions of chloroform. The combined extract was diluted to 25 ml with chloroform and its absorbance was measured at 340 nm against the reagent blank prepared under the same conditions, using the same quantity of the reagent.

Platinum: A known quantity of the platinum(IV) solution was adjusted to an acidity of 0.25N-5.0N in a separatory funnel, 1.2 ml of the DPT solution were added and digested for 5-10 minutes over a warm water-bath (70-80°C). It was cooled to room temperature. The light yellow precipitate formed was extracted with chloroform, after the addition of a few ml of ethanol as described above and the absorbance of the extract was measured at 340 nm against an appropriate reagent blank.

Alternatively, a measured amount of the platinum(IV) solution was maintained at pH 4.4-5.6 in a separatory funnel and was mixed with 1-2 ml of the DPT solution. The solution was digested for 30 minutes on a boiling water bath, cooled, a few ml of ethanol added, extracted with chloroform and the absorbance was measured at 340 nm as before.

Rhodium: An aliquot of the rhodium(III) solution was adjusted to 3.5N-5.0N in a separatory funnel and mixed with 1-2 ml of the DPT solution. The mixture was digested for about one hour on a boiling water bath and 2-3 ml of ethanol were added after cooling. The yellow complex was extracted with chloroform and

the absorbance was then measured at 340 nm as described above.

Alternatively, a measured amount of the rhodium(III) solution was adjusted to pH 3.0-5.5, required amount of the DPT solution added and warmed for 30 minutes on a boiling water-bath. The separatory funnel with its contents was cooled, 2-3 ml of ethanol added and the yellow rhodium complex was extracted with chloroform as before. The absorbance of the extract was measured at 350 nm against an appropriate reagent blank.

Iridium: A definite amount of the iridium(III) solution was maintained at pH 5.25-6.20 in a separatory funnel, 1-2 ml of the DPT solution added, warmed for about one hour on a boiling water-bath and cooled. To this, 2-3 ml of ethanol were added, the yellow complex extracted with chloroform and the absorbance was measured at 340 nm as mentioned above.

Osmium: A known amount of the osmium(VIII) solution was taken in a separatory funnel and reduced to osmium(VI) by the addition of 1-2 ml of ethanol. The solution was adjusted to 0.1N-2.5N, 2-4 ml of DPT solution added, allowed to stand for 10-15 minutes, and 2-3 ml of ethanol added. The pink precipitate formed was extracted and made to 25 ml with chloroform as before. The absorbance of the extract was then measured at 340 nm and 510 nm against the appropriate reagent blank.

Ruthenium: An aliquot of the ruthenium(III) solution was adjusted to pH 4.2-5.65 in a separatory funnel, 1-2 ml of the DPT solution added, digested on a hot water-bath for 20-30 minutes and cooled to room temperature. To this, 10 ml of ethanol were added and the brown metal complex was extracted with 5 ml portions of methylisobutylketone. The extract was diluted to 25 ml with ethanol and its absorbance was measured at 340 nm against the appropriate reagent blank.

Alternatively, a known amount of the ruthenium(III) solution was maintained at an acidity of 3.0N-4.5N and the required amount of DPT solution was added. The mixture was digested on a boiling water bath for 20-30 minutes and cooled. The blue complex formed was extracted with 5 ml portions of chloroform after the addition of 2-3 ml ethanol and the absorbance of the extract was measured at 330 nm and 610 nm against the appropriate reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

The absorbance curves of extracts of complexes formed by the platinum metals with DPT and also the absorbance curve of DPT in ethanol solution are shown in figs 1 and 2. The properties of the metal complexes under varying experimental conditions have been studied and the results are summarised in Tables 1 and 2.

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

The formation of platinum metal complexes with DPT has been studied by the mole-ratio and slope-ratio methods. The palladium(II) and osmium(VI) form 1:2 complexes in acid medium, where as rhodium(III), iridium(III) and ruthenium(III) form 1:3 complexes with DPT in acetate medium. The dissociation constants of the above complexes, as determined by

TABLE 1—PROPERTIES OF PLATINUM METAL COMPLEXES

Metal Complex	Optimum acidity range for complete extraction	λ_{max} (nm)	Adherence of Beer's law ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) at wave length (nm)
Palladium (II)	2N-6N hydrochloric acid ^r	330 ^c	0.47-5.92 (340)
Platinum (IV)	(a) 0.25-5.0 N hydrochloric acid ^h	320 ^c	2.5-13.0 (340)
	(b) pH 4.4-5.6 ^h	310 ^c	1.96-14.50 (340)
Rhodium (III)	(a) 3.5-5.0 N hydrochloric acid	315 ^c	0.29-3.45 (340)
	(b) pH 3.0-5.5 ^h	300 ^g	0.57-5.16 (350)
Iridium (III)	pH 5.25-6.20 ^h	310 ^c	1.28-14.90 (340)
Osmium (VI)	0.1N-2.5N hydrochloric acid ^r	315 ^c and 510 ^g	1.36-6.60 (340) and 3.6-34.5 (510)
		305 ^c and 610 ^g	0.6-3.5 (330) and 2.3-20.2 (610)
Ruthenium (III)	(a) 3.0N-4.5 N hydrochloric acid ^h	340 ^m	1.8-8.3 (340)
	(b) pH 4.20-5.65 ^h		

h=hot solution, *r*=room temperature, *c*=in chloroform,

m=in methylisobutylketone.

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL PARAMETERS OF PLATINUM METAL COMPLEXES

Metal complex	Optimum concentration range of metals ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)	Molar absorptivity (liter mole ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	Sensitivity ($\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$)	Coefficient of variation %	Relative mean error %
Palladium ^a	0.95 – 3.36	2.70×10^4	0.005	0.86	0.25
Platinum ^a	6.20 – 14.50	6.23×10^3	0.03	0.48	0.16
Platinum ^b	3.90 – 13.80	9.92×10^4	0.019	0.56	0.34
Rhodium ^a	1.00 – 3.57	2.06×10^4	0.005	0.72	0.26
Rhodium ^b	2.13 – 5.16	9.60×10^3	0.001	0.58	0.28
Iridium ^b	4.20 – 14.70	9.10×10^4	0.021	0.68	0.32
Osmium ^a (at 510 nm)	9.20 – 33.0	4.10×10^4	0.046	0.77	0.26
Ruthenium ^a (at 610 nm)	5.50 – 19.05	3.60×10^4	0.027	0.62	0.18
Ruthenium ^b	2.40 – 8.40	8.49×10^4	0.001	0.72	0.34

a=acid medium, b=acetate medium.

the mole-ratio method⁸, are as follows :

Complex	Dissociation constant
palladium (II)	5.39×10^{-11}
rhodium (III)	4.05×10^{-10}
iridium (III)	3.92×10^{-15}
osmium (VI)	3.61×10^{-10}
ruthenium (III)	5.70×10^{-12}

However, the dissociation constants of both the platinum(IV) complexes, and of rhodium(III) and ruthenium(III) complexes in acid medium could not be determined as large excess of DPT was required for complexation.

Effect of diverse ions: Each of the platinum metals (except iridium) was determined with DPT in acid medium in presence of commonly associated metals, following the procedure as described above. Interference studies have also been made in the determination of platinum, rhodium, ruthenium and iridium in acetate buffer medium. The results obtained in acid medium were, however, more encouraging than those in acetate medium. Proper masking agents were used to check the hydrolysis of the diverse ions, where necessary. The tolerance limit (i. e., the concentration of diverse ion causing an error less than $\pm 2\%$ in the transmittance value) in each case is indicated in Table 3.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS ON PHOTOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF PLATINUM METALS WITH DPT

Foreign ions	Amount tolerated (mg) in the determination of					
	^a Pd ⁺⁺ (47.0 μg)	^b Pt ⁺⁺ (257.5 μg)	^a Rh ⁺⁺ (57.6 μg)	^b Ir ⁺⁺ (210.0 μg)	^b Ru ⁺⁺ (250.0 μg)	^a Os ⁺⁺ (450.0 μg)
Mn(II)	2.0	1.0	2.0	2.0*	1.5	2.0
Fe(III)	2.0	1.0	2.0	2.0*	1.5	2.0
Co(II)	2.0	1.0	2.0	2.0*	1.5	2.0
Ni(II)	2.0	1.0	2.0	2.0*	1.5	2.0
Cu(II)	2.0	1.0	2.0	2.0*	1.0	1.0
Ga(III)	1.5	0.8	0.5	0.4*	0.8	0.5
Mo(VI)	0.8	0.8	0.3	0.2*	0.8	0.5
Ru(III)	1.0	0.3§	0.5§	1.0§	—	1.5
Rh(III)	1.0	0.2	—	0.1‡	2.0	2.0
Pd(II)	—	0.5‡	2.0‡	2.5‡	0.5	0.5
Cd(II)	1.5	0.4	1.5	0.4*	1.0	1.0
W(VI)	0.8§	0.8	0.3	0.2*	0.8	0.5
Os(VI)	0.5§	0.5‡	2.0‡	2.5§	2.0‡	—
Ir(III)	1.0	1.0	0.3	—	2.0	2.0
Pt(IV)	0.3	—	0.5	1.0‡	2.0	2.0
Au(III)	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.15	0.8	0.5
Hg(II)	1.5	0.4	1.0	0.4‡	1.0	1.0
Tl(III)	1.5	0.8	0.5	0.4*	0.8	0.5
Pb(II)	2.0	0.8	1.0	2.0*	1.5	2.0
U(VI)	2.0	0.8	1.5	2.0*	1.0	1.0
Th(IV)	—	—	1.0	—	1.0	1.0

a=Acid medium ; b=Acetate buffer medium ; * = Tartrate as masking agent ;
 ‡ = EDTA as masking agent ; † = Prior extraction of foreign ion with DPT ;
 § = Prior reduction with hydroxylamine hydrochloride.

Procedure for the separation and determination of platinum metals from their synthetic mixtures.

Osmium and Ruthenium : A known amount of the solution containing all the six platinum metals was taken in a 100-ml separatory funnel and 1-2 ml of ethanol were added to reduce osmium(VIII) to osmium(VI). The resulting solution was allowed to stand for 5-10 minutes, adjusted to 1.0N with dilute hydrochloric acid and excess of 0.01M DPT solution added. The mixture was stirred thoroughly, allowed to stand for 5-10 minutes and 2-3 ml of ethanol added. The pink complex of osmium formed was then extracted with 5-ml portions of chloroform. The combined extract was made to 25 ml volume with chloroform and its absorbance was measured at 510 nm against a reagent blank prepared under the same conditions with the same amount of reagent for the determination of osmium.

The acidity of the aqueous phase was then adjusted to 3.5N and mixed with an excess of the DPT solution. The solution was stirred, warmed on a hot water-bath for 30 minutes, cooled, 2-3 ml of ethanol added and the mixture was extracted with chloroform as described above. The ruthenium content of the combined extract was determined by measuring its absorbance at 610 nm against the appropriate reagent blank.

Palladium and Platinum : Another aliquot of the synthetic mixture of all the six platinum metals was adjusted to 3.0N and was either digested with sulphur dioxide solution for 40 minutes or treated with hydroxylamine hydrochloride. To the resulting solution 1-2 ml of the DPT solution added, stirred and allowed to stand for 5 minutes. The yellow palladium complex formed was then extracted with ethanol-chloroform as before, and the palladium content was determined by measuring the absorbance of the combined extract at 340 nm against the appropriate reagent blank.

The aqueous phase was boiled with 2.0 ml concentrated nitric acid and the excess of nitric acid was fumed off. The solution was cooled, boiled with perchloric acid to remove all of the osmium and ruthenium from the mixture. The solution was cooled, diluted and 1-2 ml of the DPT solution were added after adjusting its acidity to 0.25N-0.5N. The resulting solution was stirred, digested for 5-10 minutes over a warm water-bath (70°-80°C), cooled and the light yellow precipitate formed was extracted with ethanol-chloroform as above. The platinum content of the mixture was then determined by measuring the absorbance of the combined extract at 340 nm against the appropriate reagent blank.

Rhodium and Iridium : A third aliquot of the synthetic mixture of all the platinum metals was adjusted to 2.0N, excess of the DPT solution added and the mixture was warmed for 5-10 minutes on a hot water bath. The mixture was cooled and the palladium, osmium and platinum complexes formed were separated by extraction with ethanol-chloroform. To the aqueous

phase hydroxylamine hydrochloride was added to avoid the interference of ruthenium(III). The acidity of the resulting solution was adjusted to 3.5N and required amount of the DPT solution added. The mixture was stirred, warmed on a boiling water-bath for about one hour, cooled and then extracted with ethanol-chloroform. The rhodium content of the mixture was determined by measuring the absorbance of the combined extract at 340 nm against the appropriate reagent blank.

The aqueous phase containing iridium was then adjusted to pH 5.5 with dilute sodium hydroxide and sodium acetate solutions and 1- ml of the DPT solution were added. The solution was digested for one hour on a boiling bath, cooled and the light yellow iridium complex formed was extracted as before. The iridium content of the mixture was determined by measuring the absorbance of the extract at 340 nm against the appropriate reagent blank.

The results are given in Table 4.

TABLE 4—SEPARATION AND DETERMINATION OF PLATINUM METALS FROM THEIR SYNTHETIC MIXTURES.

Synthetic mixture	Metal taken (μg)	Metal found (μg)
1.	Pd (47.0); Pt (257.0) Rh(57.6); Ir (210.0) Os (450.0); Ru (250.0)	Pd (47.0); Pt (256.2) Rh(57.0); Ir (210.8) Os (451.0); Ru (250.7)
2.	Pd (71.5); Pt (177.5) Rh (40.0); Ir (152.4) Os (376.5); Ru (202.0)	Pd (71.3); Pt (176.3) Rh (39.3); Ir (152.0) Os (376.1); Ru (202.0)
3.	Pd (28.3); Pt (283.4) Rh (77.5); Ir (232.5) Os (487.5); Ru (298.0)	Pd (28.1); Pt (283.0) Rh (77.2); Ir (231.0) Os (486.3); Ru (297.6)

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